

Rotation and sliding collapse mechanisms for in plane masonry pointed arches: statistical parametric assessment

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Abstract

Pointed arches are important architectural elements of both western and eastern historical built heritage. In this paper, the effects that different geometrical (slenderness and sharpness) and mechanical (friction and cohesion) parameters have on the in-plane structural response of masonry pointed arches are investigated through the implementation of an upper bound limit analysis approach capable of representing sliding between rigid blocks. Results, in terms of collapse multipliers are presented and quantitatively analysed following a systematic statistical approach, whereas collapse mechanisms are qualitatively explored and three different outcomes are found; pure rotation, pure sliding and mixed collapse mechanisms. It is concluded that the capacity of the numerical approach implemented to reproduce sliding between blocks plays a major role in the better understanding of masonry pointed arches structural response.

Keywords: Non-standard Limit Analysis, Friction/Dilatancy, No-tension contacts, Pointed arches, Cohesion

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1. Introduction

Pointed arches are well known as representative elements of the Gothic style in western architecture. However, according to certain authors, pointed arches first appeared in Persian architecture, during the Sassanid Empire (third to seventh century AD) and then were adopted by muslim architecture at the beginning of the eighth century. According to Viollet-le-duc, pointed arches were found both in Persia and Egypt as early as the sixth century and this architectural element was not introduced in Europe until the twelfth century [1]. Figure 1 presents an example of pointed arches used in western architecture (Figure 1a) and in muslim architecture (Figure 1b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: Examples of pointed arches in: (a) western architecture, Brussels cathedral windows, Belgium and (b) muslim architecture, El Badi palace at Marrakech, Morocco.

Despite the fact that it has been well known for a long time that pointed arches have a different structural behaviour in comparison to circular arches, i.e. classic geometric rules prescribed thinner abutments for pointed arches than for circular arches [1], relatively little attention has been paid to the formal structural study of the former. Aita *et. al* [2] studied the equilibrium of circular, pointed and elliptical arches subjected to their own self-weight plus the superimposed weight of a masonry wall. They applied

the Durand-Claye's method and a nonlinear one-dimensional elastic analysis and found that pointed and elliptical arches had a better behavior in comparison to circular ones in terms of wall height that can be carried by the arch.

Lengyel and Bagi [3] studied the effect that excentricity had in the horizontal reac-
20 tion of pointed vaults (elements created through the out-of-plane extrusion of pointed arches) by implementing a Timoshenko beam theory based analytical model and discrete element method (DEM) simulated experimental results. Their main findings were in agreement with previous research and reinforced the concept that pointed arches exert smaller horizontal thrust than circular ones.

25 A closed-form expression that serves to evaluate the minimum thickness of a pointed arch under its own self-weight was derived by Nikolić [4]. He implemented an extended geometric formulation, originally proposed by Milankovitch, that considered the macroscopic equilibrium analysis of a portion of the pointed arch. Through this approach, Nikolić concluded that four collapse mechanisms including five, six or seven
30 hinges could develop when the arch reaches a limit equilibrium state. This author also ran a parametric analysis and presented a graph and a table with minimum thickness values based on eccentricity and embrace angles of different pointed arches.

Cavalagli *et. al* [5] and Brandonisio *et. al* [6] consider the effect of the uncertain dimension of the blocks and the effect of the buttresses on the seismic capacity of
35 arches, respectively. Misseri and Rovero [7] adopted the Heyman's hypothesis and analysed the seismic vulnerability of pointed arches through a parametric analysis that explored arch slenderness and sharpness. Based on their results, it is now known that the pattern of hinges at collapse for pointed arches differs considerably from the one of

circular arches, that slenderness and sharpness are significant on the pattern of collapse
40 hinges and that the acceleration to start motion is directly proportional to arch rise in
pointed arches, contrary to the case of circular ones.

Also by adopting Heyman's hypothesis, Cavalagli *et. al* [8] studied the limit equilibrium condition and the minimum thickness of circular and pointed masonry arches subjected to vertical self-weight plus a horizontal proportional live load. They provided
45 a series of surface plots from which the collapse multiplier of either type of arch could be determined based on their geometry parameter values.

Misseri *et. al* [9] performed an experimental campaign in which they studied the response of pointed arches subjected to vertical self-weight and a proportional horizontal live load for different values of slenderness and sharpness by means of a tilting table.
50 They identified two types of collapse mechanism: pure rotation and rotation/sliding combination (their experimental set-up prevented the formation of pure sliding collapse mechanisms).

In a recent application of Durand-Claye's method, Aita *et. al* [10] presented the characteristic mechanical behaviour and collapse of symmetric circular, low-pointed,
55 equilateral-pointed and lancet-pointed arches subjected to self-weight for which friction coefficient and compressive strength was taken into account. Later on they extended their work to the analysis of the same arches typologies supported on piers [11]. Moreover, Galassi *et. al* [12] studied the vulnerability of masonry pointed arches subjected to support displacements through a novel numerical approach that uses com-
60 binatorial laws and adopts Heyman's assumptions. Further studies on pointed arches have been summarized and presented by Lengyel [13].

According to the observations made by Romano and Ochsendorf [14] it could be said from the structural behaviour of pointed arches that:

- Pointed arches have lower horizontal thrust than circular arches.
- 65 • Under symmetrical conditions, the thrust line of a circular arch touches the extrados at only one location, whereas that on a pointed arch, due to its geometry, the thrust line has to touch the extrados twice and for extremely thin pointed arches it touches twice the extrados and once the intrados.
- With the exception of arches with low embrace angles, pointed arches can be
70 narrower than their circular counterparts in most practical geometries.
- Pointed arches subjected to horizontal support spreading are able to deform substantially more than circular ones.
- Pointed arches are able to withstand higher concentrated loads at the crown in comparison to the circular ones.

75 The modeling and assessment of masonry structural response is a challenging task due to the variability and heterogeneity of masonry and the influence of geometrical factors on its behavior. Several authors have proposed a number of numerical procedures to simulate masonry structural behavior at different scales and levels of detail throughout the last few decades [15, 16, 17]. The so-called block-based models (BBM),
80 as classified by D'Altri *et al.* [17], are one of the most suitable modeling strategies for capturing masonry structural response. The approach relies on discrete modeling of every masonry block along with a suitable formulation to represent the inter-block

interface interactions. In this context, two numerical approach are of special importance: DEM and Limit Analysis (LA). DEM methods are capable of reproducing large
85 displacements, cracking and sliding of masonry blocks. They have been widely implemented on the study of masonry arches and bridges [18, 19, 20, 21, 22]. LA enables the determination of the ultimate load capacity of the structure and its corresponding failure mechanism, with only a few material parameters, eliminating the common difficulties of acquiring reliable experimental data for historical masonry structures given
90 their sensitive nature. Furthermore, LA is well acknowledged as a very effective tool regarding masonry structures in the estimation of the collapse load and collapse mechanisms [23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30] or their response in the presence of settlements [31, 32, 33].

ALMA 2.0 is a new version of the original *ALMA* code (Analisi Limite Murature
95 Attritive) based on LA [34, 35, 36], which has been developed based on the work of [24]. The new version of *ALMA* overcomes the limit in terms of number of blocks with respect to the original version [24], and it has been improved to take into account foundation settlement [32], cohesion between the joints, and retrofitting tie [34] thanks to the adoption of the recent coding language *PythonTM* and the advantages of the
100 novel optimization subroutine, such as *MOSEK* library (www.mosek.com). *ALMA 2.0*'s ability to simulate the structural response of in-plane masonry pointed arches has previously been validated [37] utilizing Misseri *et al.*'s [9] experimental data and numerical simulations as a benchmark.

Using a non-standard analysis approach, the influence of various geometrical and
105 mechanical parameters on the in-plane structural response of masonry pointed arches is

examined in this study. In particular the adopted approach is based on the one provided in [23, 24], in which authors demonstrated that a non associative problem with friction can be approximated by a standard, associative, approach where friction has been replaced by dilatancy. In this way, the peculiar effect of the sliding mechanism, which
110 can occur also in the arches with high value of thickness, may be taken into account in the analysis performed.

The main distinction between this study and parametric analysis performed by other authors is that the authors used a systematic statistical method that enabled to not only identify, but also quantify, the influence that the many factors evaluated have on the
115 structural response of masonry pointed arches. Furthermore, the numerical approach implemented had the capacity of representing sliding between blocks, which has allowed to overpass the Heyman's assumption of infinite inter-block friction. This feature has allowed the authors to better capturing and understanding the structural behaviour of masonry pointed arches. The remainig of this paper is structured as follows: Section
120 2 describes the non-standard limit analysis that was employed, followed by Section 3 which describes the systematic parametric analysis that was performed. Section 4 shows and discusses the results obtained in terms of collapse multipliers and collapse mechanisms. The key findings gained from the analysis and discussion of the data are finally summarized in Section 5.

125 **2. Adopted Model**

Limit Analysis of systems of rigid blocks interacting through non-tension and frictional interfaces is considered. In this case the normality rule does not hold and the

problem is non-associative and can be solved using non-linear programming procedures [23, 24]. It is known differently, that, when normality rule holds the static and kinematic theorems of Limit Analysis lead to two dual problems of linear programming, with a unique solution. Mousavian *et al.* [38] compares the differences between the associative and non-associative sliding problems and in the case of flat joints the associative sliding capacity is similar in comparison with the non-associative one having v shaped interlocking. Moreover, Bagio and Trovalusci [23] show that the differences, whether taking into consideration non-associative or associative sliding, although not negligible, are minor. Therefore the authors decided to focus on the linear programming optimization problem (initially developed in the seminal paper by [39] following a lower bound approach). In particular, to overcome problem related to the solution of the non-associative problem, reference is made to the approach in [24], where friction is replaced by dilatancy obtaining a linearized programming problem, which provides collapse mechanisms and collapse load of analysed structures.

Following this idea, linear programming has been performed taking into account both rotation and sliding mechanisms at the interfaces between blocks. The adopted kinematic upper bound problem is defined as:

$$\alpha_c = \min \left\{ \boldsymbol{\lambda}^T \left[\mathbf{c} - (\mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{N}_1)^T \mathbf{f}_0 \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

subjected to:

$$(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{N}_1 - \mathbf{N}_2) \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \mathbf{0}, \text{ compatibility condition}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}^T (\mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{N}_1)^T \mathbf{f}_L - 1 = 0, \text{ normalized positive work of live loads}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda} \geq \mathbf{0} \text{ bounds on the unknowns.}$$

145 In the above equations the unknown of the problem remains α_c , a scalar, as the collapse multiplier with $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ as the plastic multiplier vector that contains the nonnegative coefficients. \mathbf{A}_0 is the inverse matrix of the compatibility kinematical submatrix of maximum rank while the rest of the kinematical matrix \mathbf{B}_2 is stored in the \mathbf{A} matrix as $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{B}_2 \mathbf{B}_1^{-1}$. \mathbf{N}_1 and \mathbf{N}_2 are the submatrices of the block-diagonal gradient matrix
150 \mathbf{N} and correspond to the submatrix of independent and linearly dependent kinematical variables, respectively. \mathbf{f}_0 and \mathbf{f}_L are the vectors of the generalized actions on the centres of the blocks for the dead and live loads, respectively. Additional details on the derivations and formulation of the LP problem can be consulted in [40, 23]. Different cohesion values can be assigned to every joint of the masonry assemblage. These
155 values are stored in the form of a vector \mathbf{c} . A Mohr-Coulomb classical yield domain is considered with the inclusion of cohesion, thus indirectly involving tensile strength of the joints as $\sigma_t = \mathbf{c} / \tan \phi$, for σ_t as the tensile strength and ϕ as the friction angle. After some algebraic operations the \mathbf{c} vector is stored in the objective function to be minimized through LP.

160 3. Numerical simulations

A systematic methodology has been followed in order to objectively determine the influence of several mechanical and geometrical parameters in the response of pointed

arches. Thus, general full factorial designs were used to identify both the main and the two-way interaction effects of the studied parameters on the pointed arches response.

165 blueIt is worth noting that there is no randomness associated to any of the parameters studied in this work. The selected values of the different levels of each parameter were carefully assigned based on feasible ranges as explained in the following paragraphs.

Two load scenarios were considered. For the first load scenario, every block of the pointed arches were subjected to their own self-weight plus a horizontal live load
170 proportional to their self-weight (see Figure 2a). Henceforth this will be referred as load scenario A. In the second load scenario, every block of the pointed arches was subjected to their own self-weight (as in load scenario A), but only one block at the time was subjected to a vertical concentrated live load proportional the self-weight of the block itself (see Figure 2b, where it is indicated that the live load is being applied
175 to voussoir number 12, but depending on the factor value the load could be applied to either voussoir number 8, 10, 12 or 14). Hereon, this will be referred as load scenario B. The factors considered for each load scenario and their correspondent levels (in this context, a level refers to a particular value adopted by a parameter or factor) are presented in Table 1.

180 Mathematically speaking the values that could be adopted for the friction angle ϕ (in degrees) could lay within the interval $0 < \phi < 90$. Moreover, masonry friction angles have been experimentally determined by several researchers in the past and the values reported oscillate between the 17 and the 63 degrees [41]. However, most commonly friction angle values for historical masonry vary between 15 and 45 degrees
185 and more specifically for arches between 25 and 45 degrees. Therefore, the different

Figure 2: Load scenario A (a) and load scenario B (b).

levels for friction, $\tan\phi$, studied were 0.47, 0.60, 0.84 and 1.00 which correspond to 25, 30, 40 and 45 degrees respectively. The low friction values adopted would represent a situation in which the units surface were relatively smooth, whereas that a rough surface would be better represented by the high friction values assumed.

190 The geometrical parameters, sharpness and slenderness, are better understood having as reference Figure 3. In this figure, the center of the arch is indicated by O . The arch has a radius of curvature R_p and it is drawn with two circles that have their corresponding center points at points C_1 and C_2 which are located at an eccentricity distance e from the arch center O . t indicates the thickness of the arch and R_i and R_e represent
 195 the internal and the external radius of the arch measured from the corresponding eccentric centers C_1 and C_2 . Finally, R_c is the distance from O to the center of the arch at its base.

Slenderness is defined as the ratio between the thickness of the arch and its radius, $S_d = t/R_c$. Sharpness is equal to the division of the arch eccentricity by the distance
 200 from O to the center of the arch at its base, $S_h = e/R_c$. The numerical values for

Table 1: Studied factors and their respective levels for a pointed arch subjected to load scenario A and B.

Scenario A			Scenario B*		
Factor	Level	Value	Factor	Level	Value
A. Cohesion (MPa)	1. Low	0.00	A. Cohesion (MPa)	1. Low	0.00
	2. Medium	0.01		2. Medium	0.01
	3. High	0.10		3. High	0.10
B. Friction (-)	1. Lowest	0.47	B. Friction (-)	1. Lowest	0.47
	2. Low	0.60		2. Low	0.60
	3. High	0.84		3. High	0.84
	4. Highest	1.00		4. Highest	1.00
C. Sharpness (-)	1. Low	0.20	C. Slenderness (-)	1. Lowest	0.10
	2. Medium	0.60		2. Low	0.15
	3. High	1.00		3. High	0.20
		4. Highest		0.25	
D. Slenderness (-)	1. Lowest	0.10	D. Live load location (block number)	1. Lowest	8
	2. Low	0.15		2. Low	10
	3. High	0.20		3. High	12
	4. Highest	0.25		4. Highest	14

*All arches under load scenario B have a Sharpness value of 1.00.

Slenderness and Sharpness adopted in this work correspond to those experimentally reported by [9] and numerically validated by [37]. It is worth noting here that according to the definition of slenderness provided by Misseri *et al.* [9], and also implemented in this work, the thicker is the arch, the higher the value of slenderness will be. This

Figure 3: Schematic geometry of the pointed arches simulated.

205 concept may seem contrary to the reader familiar with the concept of slenderness of a column, where thinner cross sections lead to lower values of slenderness. Thus, caution is advised during the interpretation of the results reported in this paper. Therefore, the combination of three sharpness values and four slenderness values resulted in the twelve arches shown in Figure 4.

210 The live load location parameter makes reference to the voussoir to which the concentrated live load is applied (see the values of the live load factor in Table 1). All pointed arches modeled in this study have been formed by 17 blocks, 16 voussoirs and a key block. The numbers assigned to each block are shown in Figure 5.

To the extend of the knowledge of the authors of this paper, there are no cohesion
 215 values reported in the literature for the specific case of pointed arches. In a comparative experimental work, Jafari *et al.* [42] reported a series of cohesion values obtained through testing of different masonry typology cores and triplets. The cohesion values

Figure 4: Geometries of the simulated arches.

obtained from the shear tests on cores ranged from 0.13 up to 0.49 MPa, whereas that the values obtained from the triplets ranged from 0.08 up to 0.54 MPa. Through the
 220 implementation of a static penetrometer, Liberatore *et al.* [43] determined the cohesion values of several decayed historical masonry walls mortar. The cohesion values reported by these authors ranged from 0.02 up to 0.03 MPa. On Bejarano-Urrego *et al.* [44] a table with values for different masonry joints properties is presented. The values for cohesion, based on the information reported by several authors, vary from

Figure 5: Numbers assigned to every block of the modeled pointed arches.

225 0.1 to 1.8 MPa. By testing a series of triplets created with different masonry units and mortar, Milosevic *et al.* [45] determined cohesion values in the range of 0.2 - 1.6 MPa. These authors also tested a series of stone masonry wallettes through the diagonal compression test for which they obtained cohesion values in the range of 0.017 and 0.313 MPa. Furthermore, they compared the values they obtained through their experimental
 230 campaign with the ones reported in the literature which ranged between the 0.02 and the 0.16 MPa.

The cohesion values that are adopted to perform numerical analysis depend significantly in the numerical approach followed. Rafiee and Vinches [46] simulated the structural response of stone masonry arches with the use of a non-smooth contact dy-
 235 namics method. For their simulations, these authors adopted for their models cohesion values of 0.010 and 0.007 for the normal and tangential cohesion thresholds parameters respectively. Masi *et al.* [47] adopted cohesion values ranging from 0.0 to 3.0 MPa to perform a sensitivity analysis of arched masonry structures under blast loads using a discrete element method based-approach. Weed *et al.* [48] adopted cohesion val-
 240 ues of 0.67 and 0.116 MPa to simulate the interface cohesion of cement stabilized soil block masonry walls subjected to four-point out-of-plane bending using a finite element

method based-approach. On recent numerical calibrations of irregular stone masonry walls, Zhang and Beyer [49] implemented a cohesion value of 0.3 MPa to describe the properties of their finite element model. In this work, a null cohesion value has
245 been adopted to simulate the structural response of dry stone masonry pointed arches. Moreover, relatively low values of cohesion (0.01 and 0.10 MPa) have been adopted to better represent the condition of historical stone masonry pointed arches with decayed or damaged mortar.

Other important simulation parameters adopted in this work correspond to the out-
250 of-plane depth of the blocks, which was assumed to be fixed for all arches at a value of 50 mm as well as a constant specific weight of 1800 kg/m³. As this was a numerical experiment, the basic principles of randomization, replication and blocking resulted trivial.

Following the completion of all simulations, the responses (collapse multipliers)
255 were visually analyzed using main effects and two-way interaction effects graphs. The main effect graphs make it possible to observe the real influence of each parameter on the response. The response is considered to be independent of the other parameters by computing the mean values at each level of each parameter. Two-way (or higher order) interaction plots, on the contrary, permit the investigation of the probable interaction
260 between two or more parameters and how it impacts the response. By averaging the values of α_c , obtained for a given combination of two parameters' levels, it was able to compute the points of a two-way interaction plot. Furthermore, the collapse multipliers obtained were formally analysed through an analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the importance magnitude of each one of the main factors and factor interaction effects are

265 presented as Pareto charts of standardized effect.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Collapse mechanisms

4.1.1. Collapse mechanisms under load scenario A

Regarding the collapse mechanisms of the pointed arches under load scenario A
270 and for the specific case of null cohesion (dry stone masonry), it could be said that
three different outcomes were observed: pure rotation, pure sliding and rotation-sliding
collapse modes. The pure rotation collapse mode appeared mainly on slender pointed
arches and in medium-slender pointed arches with high friction ratio values such as the
example arches shown in Figure 6. The pure sliding collapse mode only developed for
275 the pointed arch with a sharpness value of 1.00, a slender value of 0.25 and a friction
ratio of 0.47 (see Figure 7). Finally, the combination of rotation/sliding collapse mode
was the most common one developed by the pointed arches studied as can be seen in
the arches of Figure 8.

Figure 6: Rotation collapse mechanisms of dry masonry (null cohesion values) slender pointed arches or with relatively high friction values under load scenario A.

Figure 7: Sliding collapse mechanisms of pointed arch with Friction 0.47, null cohesion, Slenderness 0.25 and Sharpness 1.00 under load scenario A, $\alpha_c = 0.30370$.

(a) Friction ratio 0.47, Slenderness 0.20, Sharpness 0.60 and $\alpha_c = 0.22857$.

(b) Friction ratio 0.60, Slenderness 0.20, Sharpness 0.60 and $\alpha_c = 0.25819$.

(c) Friction ratio 0.84, Slenderness 0.20, Sharpness 0.60 and $\alpha_c = 0.31495$.

(d) Friction ratio 1.00, Slenderness 0.20, Sharpness 0.60 and $\alpha = 0.34739$.

Figure 8: Combined collapse mechanisms for dry masonry pointed arches under load scenario A.

The collapse mechanisms observed for the no-cohesion cases were clearly modified
 280 by the inclusion of cohesion. For cohesion values of 0.01 MPa only pure rotation and
 rotation-sliding mechanisms developed, whereas that only rotation mechanisms were
 obtained for the pointed arches with a cohesion value of 0.10 MPa. The most clear
 example of the role that cohesion plays in the collapse mechanism of the pointed arches
 studied can be observed for an arch with a slenderness value of 0.10 and a sharpness
 285 value of 0.25. Figure 9 presents the collapse mechanisms obtained for this arch for
 cohesion values of 0.00 MPa (a), 0.01 MPa (b) and 0.10 MPa (c) (and a friction ratio
 value of 0.47). The collapse mechanism obtained for the dry stone masonry arch (no-
 cohesion) was of pure sliding, the one for the arch with an intermediate cohesion value
 (0.01 MPa) was of the combined rotation-sliding type whereas that a pure rotation
 290 collapse mechanism was obtained for the arch with a relatively high cohesion value
 (0.10 MPa).

Figure 9: Effects of cohesion in the collapse mechanisms of pointed arches under load scenario A.

4.1.2. Collapse mechanisms under load scenario B

The effect that cohesion, friction ratio and slenderness have in the collapse mechanism of pointed arches has already been discussed in a previous section for the case of pointed arches under load scenario B. Similar observation could be made about these parameters for the case of pointed arches under load scenario B. On the other hand, the effect that the location of the live load has in the response of pointed arches is presented now. The collapse mechanisms obtained for pointed arches with a medium value of cohesion (0.01 MPa), a low slenderness value (0.15), a low friction ratio (0.60) and the live load applied at blocks 8, 10, 12 and 14 is presented in Figure 10 (a), (b), (c) and (d) respectively. As it can be observed, the effect of placing the live load in either blocks 8 or 10 will lead to a pure rotation mechanism, whereas that if the live load is applied in either blocks 12 or 14, the collapse mechanism generated is of the combined rotation-sliding type.

4.2. Collapse multipliers

4.2.1. Collapse multipliers under load scenario A

After running the limit analysis numerical simulations of all the pointed arches subjected to their own self weight plus a horizontal live load proportional to their self-weight (load scenario A) as described in Section 3, the corresponding collapse multipliers were obtained. These values were used to determine if any of the analyzed parameters had a statistically significant influence in the response. To do so, the mean value of α_c was computed at every level for all individual factors and combination of two factors. The main effect plots are shown in Figure 11 and the two-way interaction plots are presented in Figure 12.

(a) Live load applied to block 8, $\alpha_c = 32.25203$.

(b) Live load applied to block 10, $\alpha_c = 19.74183$.

(c) Live load applied to block 12, $\alpha_c = 13.30609$.

(d) Live load applied to block 14, $\alpha_c = 9.20905$.

Figure 10: Effect of the live load location parameter on the collapse mechanisms under load scenario B.

315 From Figure 11 it can be observed that all factors present a positive relation with the response (the higher is the value of the factor, the higher is the collapse multiplier obtained). Both friction ratio and sharpness have a relatively weak effect on the response whereas that cohesion and slenderness present a strong relation.

From the first row of the curves shown in Figure 12 it can be observed that there is
 320 no statistically significant effect between cohesion-friction interactions, as the average

Figure 11: Main effect plots for load scenario A.

α_c values at the different levels of the combined parameters are practically identical as well as the variability of results obtained at the different levels combinations. Although the slenderness-sharpness curves (observed in the lower right part of Figure 12) present higher values of average collapse multipliers for higher values of slenderness, it can be

 325 observed that the variability of the response is quite identical at the three levels of sharpness, thus showing that this two-way interaction term does not cause significant effects on the response. On the other hand, a clear two-way interaction effect is detected for the two-way parameter interaction of cohesion-slenderness. At a null cohesion value (dry stone masonry) the response varies slightly for the different levels of slenderness. As

 330 the cohesion value increases, so does the variability of the response for the higher val-

Figure 12: Interaction effect plots for load scenario A.

ues of slenderness, a significantly higher collapse multiplier is obtained in comparison with the lower values of slenderness. There is a similar effect in the response caused by the two-way parameter interactions of friction-slenderness, friction-sharpness and cohesion-sharpness. Although the variability of the response (relatively higher collapse
 335 multipliers for the higher values of the mentioned parameters combinations) is not as visually obvious as for the cohesion-slenderness combination, it could be considered that these three two-way terms affect the response in a significant way as well.

To verify the assumptions adopted after the visual examination of Figures 11 and 12, the collapse multipliers obtained were analysed through an analysis of variance

340 (ANOVA). Table 2 presents the ANOVA results performed using the software *Minitab*
(<https://www.minitab.com/en-us/>). In the first column of Table 2 the sta-
tistical model terms are identified by their names, in the second column the degrees
of freedom (DoF) of every term are presented, in the third column the adjusted sum
of squares (Adj SS) corresponding to every term are shown and in column four the
345 adjusted mean squares (Adj MS) are listed. In the fifth column of the ANOVA table we
can see the value corresponding to the F statistical test and finally, in the last column of
Table 2, the corresponding P-Values to each term are presented. At a confidence level
of 95%, the terms with a $P - Value < 0.05$ are considered to be statistically signifi-
cant. Thus, besides from the cohesion-friction and the sharpness-slenderness two-way
350 interaction terms, the rest of the terms in the statistic model adopted are considered to
have a significant effect in the response of the pointed arches studied.

Moreover, the magnitude and importance of each one of the main factors and factor
interaction effects were obtained. In Figure 13 it can be seen that besides from the
cohesion-friction and the sharpness-slenderness, all other terms on the statistical model
355 resulted to have a significant effect in the response (as they all have a standardized
effect value greater than the significance threshold of 1.985). All single parameter
terms along with the two-way cohesion-slenderness interaction term were the terms
of the model with a higher influence in the collapse multiplier value of the simulated
values. These terms are followed in order of importance by the friction-sharpness and
360 cohesion-sharpness terms, and finally by the friction-slenderness two-way interaction
effect.

Regarding the suitability of the adopted statistical model to describe the response,

Figure 13: Pareto chart of the standardized effects: magnitude and importance of the different main factors and factor interactions effects for load scenario A.

the values of the coefficient of determination, R^2 and of the predicted coefficient of determination, R^2_{pred} , obtained were of 99.79% and 99.53% respectively. This proves the good fit and the high prediction capabilities of the model adopted and allows to maintain the cohesion term of the statistical model as linear.

The data independence and data normality assumptions were visually validated by analyzing the standardized residual plots of the response, α_c , its histogram and its normal probability plot. In the normal probability plot of Figure 14 (upper right plot) it could be observed that most of the points were relatively close to the diagonal line and only a few outliers were present (one observation with a standardized residual value smaller than three and three observation with a value greater than three), which did not affect significantly the validity of the statistical model adopted. Furthermore, it could be observed that the histogram on Figure 14 resembles to a Gauss distribution and that no clear structure is present on the Versus Fits nor on the Versus order plots of the standardized residuals in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Normal probability, histogram and standardized residual plots for the pointed arches under load scenario A.

4.2.2. Collapse multipliers under load scenario B

As per the pointed arches subjected to a load scenario A, similar data was obtained and analyzed per the pointed arches under load scenario B. The main effect plots are shown in Figure 15 and the two-way interaction plots are presented in Figure 380 16. Table 2 presents the ANOVA results and Figure 17 the Pareto chart of standardized effects.

From Figure 15 it can be observed that both cohesion and slenderness have a strong positive relationship with the response, namely the higher the cohesion or the slenderness, the higher would be the value of α_c . The friction ratio parameter presents 385

Figure 15: Main effect plots for load scenario B.

a relatively weak positive relation with the response. Finally, the live load location parameter plays an important role in the collapse multiplier value obtained from the pointed arches simulated under load scenario B. It can be observed that the closer the live load is applied to the key stone (see Figure 5), the lower will be the collapse multiplier obtained. From the curves of Figure 15 it can be seen that there is a non-linear

390 relation between slenderness and live load location with the response of the pointed arch under load scenario B. Unfortunately, the terms for the individual parameters in the statistical model adopted are linear and this has cause some low values for the suitability, $R^2 = 83.57\%$, and the prediction, $R^2_{pred} = 66.77\%$, capabilities of the adopted

395 statistical model. The statistical model could be further improved through a parameter

Figure 16: Interaction effect plots for load scenario B.

transformation (adopting quadratic or exponential terms for the mentioned parameters) but that is outside the scope of this paper.

From the two-way interaction curves of Figure 16 it can be observed that cohesion-slenderness, cohesion-live load and slenderness-live load parameter interactions have a statistically significant effect of the response of pointed arches under load scenario B. The values obtained for the response changes significantly for the different parameter combinations mentioned (similar $\langle \alpha_c \rangle$ values for the lower values of cohesion and slenderness regardless of the value of the second parameter, whereas relatively significant variation on the $\langle \alpha_c \rangle$ values for the higher values of cohesion and slenderness).

Figure 17: Pareto chart of the standardized effects: magnitude and importance of the different main factors and factor interactions effects for load scenario B.

405 The response values obtained for the two-way cohesion-friction term are practically identical for all different parameter combinations and although clear higher response values are obtained for the two-way friction-slenderness and friction-live load interaction for the cases of slenderness equal to 0.25 and live load applied at voussoir 8 respectively, this wouldn't be enough to consider that this interaction terms had a significant

410 effect on the response. Moreover, these visual assumptions are reinforced by the results obtained from the ANOVA analysis of the $\langle \alpha_c \rangle$ values obtained. It can be seen in Table 3 that not only the cohesion-friction two-way interaction term is not statistically significant, but the friction-slenderness and the friction-live load are as well considered as not statistically significant. Finally, in Figure 17 it can be seen that cohesion, slenderness

415 and live load location parameters along with the cohesion-slenderness, slenderness-live load location and cohesion-live load location are the terms of the statistical model adopted which have a significant effect in the value of the collapse multiplier obtained for pointed arches under load scenario B.

The data independence and data normality assumptions were unfortunately not satisfied by the statistical model adopted. From the histogram presented in Figure 18, a certain degree of skewness is clearly observed. This observation, along with the presence of several outlier points in the standardized residual plots of Figure 18, reinforce the evidence observed regarding the non-linear relation between the parameters studied and the response of pointed arches under load scenario B and suggests that a parameter transformation (adoption of quadratic or exponential terms for the cohesion, slenderness and live load location terms) may be necessary in order to improve the quality of the statistical assessment of the results obtained for pointed arches under load scenario B.

Figure 18: Normal probability, histogram and standardized residual plots for the pointed arches under load scenario B.

5. Conclusions

430 The parametric analysis presented in this paper allowed to objectively identify the effect that slenderness, sharpness, friction ratio, cohesion and live load location parameters have in the collapse multiplier value and in the collapse mechanism of a masonry pointed arch using a non-standard limit analysis approach. The main findings drawn from this work are:

- 435 • Three different collapse mechanisms were observed for the studied pointed arches subjected to load scenario A: pure rotation, pure shearing and combined rotation-shearing mechanisms. On the other hand, only pure rotation and combined rotation-shearing mechanisms were obtained for the pointed arches subjected to load scenario B.
- 440 • Contrary to what has been previously pointed out by several authors, no statistically significant effect was found for the two-way sharpness-slenderness parameter on the response of pointed arches.
- 445 • The mechanical parameters studied play an important role in the value of collapse multipliers computed for the case of pointed arches subjected to load scenario A, whereas that only cohesion resulted to be statistically significant for the case of pointed arches subjected to load scenario B.
- 450 • Pointed arches can sustain larger concentrated loads if they are applied closer to the arch haunches than to its keystone. This conclusion has been drawn based on the main effect plot presented in Figure 15 where it can be observed that for a live load applied at block number 8 (which is close to the arch haunches), an average

collapse multiplier of around 230 was obtained, whereas that for the live load applied at block 14 (close to the arch key stone), the average collapse multiplier was of only about 30. It is worth noting here though that these observations are only valid within the explored region, in other words, this conclusion cannot be
455 extrapolated to make inference about the possible collapse multiplier value that would be obtained if the live load were applied at a different block number.

- For the load scenario A, all individual parameters as well as the cohesion-slenderness two way interaction resulted to have the biggest standardized effect with a computed value of 7.588. Friction-sharpness and cohesion-sharpness had standardized
460 effects of 6.088 and 6.078 respectively. A smaller, but still statistically significant, standardized effect of 2.980 was found for the friction-slenderness two-way interaction parameter.
- Cohesion, slenderness, live load location and the two-way interaction parameters cohesion-slenderness, slenderness-live load location and cohesion-live load
465 location presented a standardized effect value of 7.306. The cohesion-live load location two way interaction also resulted into an important standardized effect value of 6.797.

6. Data availability statement

Some or all data, models, or code generated or used during the study are available
470 in a repository or online in accordance with funder data retention policies [50].

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Appendix A: ANOVA and statistical concepts

480 In order to make this paper self-consistent, this appendix presents the basic statistics and ANOVA concepts implemented. Further details can be found in well known statistics textbooks [51, 52].

In a four factor design there will be a levels of factor A , b levels of factor B , c levels of factor C and d levels of factor D . Thus, there will be $abcd$ total observations. Thus,
485 a four-factor ANOVA which considers only main effects and two-way interactions could be expressed as shown in Equation A.1:

$$\begin{aligned}
y_{ijkl} = & \mu + \tau_i + \beta_j + \gamma_k + \chi_l \\
& + (\tau\beta)_{ij} + (\tau\gamma)_{ik} + (\tau\chi)_{il} + (\beta\gamma)_{jk} + (\beta\chi)_{jl} + (\gamma\chi)_{kl} \\
& + \epsilon_{ijkl}, \\
i = & 1, 2, \dots, a, \\
j = & 1, 2, \dots, b, \\
k = & 1, 2, \dots, c, \\
l = & 1, 2, \dots, d
\end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$

where μ is the overall mean effect, τ_i is the effect of the i th level of factor A , β_j is the effect of the j th level of factor B , γ_k is the effect of the k th level of factor C , χ_l is the effect of the l th level of factor D , $(\tau\beta)_{ij}$ is the interaction effect between τ_i and β_j , $(\tau\gamma)_{ik}$ is the interaction effect between τ_i and γ_k , $(\tau\chi)_{il}$ is the interaction effect between τ_i and χ_l , $(\beta\gamma)_{jk}$ is the interaction effect between β_j and γ_k , $(\beta\chi)_{jl}$ is the interaction effect between β_j and χ_l , $(\gamma\chi)_{kl}$ is the interaction effect between γ_k and χ_l and ϵ_{ijkl} is a random error component.

All factors are assumed to be fixed and the treatment effects, as well as the interaction effects, are defined as deviations from the overall mean as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=1}^a \tau_i &= 0, \\
\sum_{j=1}^b \beta_j &= 0, \\
\sum_{k=1}^c \gamma_k &= 0, \\
\sum_{l=1}^d \chi_l &= 0, \\
\sum_{i=1}^a (\tau\beta)_{ij} &= \sum_{j=1}^b (\tau\beta)_{ij} = 0, \\
\sum_{i=1}^a (\tau\gamma)_{ik} &= \sum_{k=1}^c (\tau\gamma)_{ik} = 0, \\
\sum_{i=1}^a (\tau\chi)_{il} &= \sum_{l=1}^d (\tau\chi)_{il} = 0, \\
\sum_{j=1}^b (\beta\gamma)_{jk} &= \sum_{k=1}^c (\beta\gamma)_{jk} = 0, \\
\sum_{j=1}^b (\beta\chi)_{jl} &= \sum_{l=1}^d (\beta\chi)_{jl} = 0, \\
\sum_{k=1}^c (\gamma\chi)_{kl} &= \sum_{l=1}^d (\gamma\chi)_{kl} = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{A.2}$$

The ANOVA, sometimes referred to as significance of regression test, allows to determine whether there is a relationship between the parameters of the statistical model (also known as regressor variables) and the response. The hypotheses of the ANOVA test are:

$$H_0 : \tau_1 = \tau_2 = \dots \tau_a = 0 \tag{A.3.1}$$

$$H_1 : \tau_i \neq 0 \text{ for at least one } i \tag{A.3.2}$$

$$H_0 : \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \dots \beta_b = 0 \quad (\text{A.3.3})$$

$$H_1 : \beta_j \neq 0 \text{ for at least one } j \quad (\text{A.3.4})$$

$$H_0 : \gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = \dots \gamma_c = 0 \quad (\text{A.3.5})$$

$$H_1 : \gamma_k \neq 0 \text{ for at least one } k \quad (\text{A.3.6})$$

$$H_0 : \chi_1 = \chi_2 = \dots \chi_d = 0 \quad (\text{A.3.7})$$

$$H_1 : \chi_l \neq 0 \text{ for at least one } l \quad (\text{A.3.8})$$

$$H_0 : (\tau\beta)_{ij} = 0 \text{ for all } i, j \quad (\text{A.3.9})$$

$$H_1 : (\tau\beta)_{ij} \neq 0 \text{ for at least one } i, j \quad (\text{A.3.10})$$

$$H_0 : (\tau\gamma)_{ik} = 0 \text{ for all } i, k \quad (\text{A.3.11})$$

$$H_1 : (\tau\gamma)_{ik} \neq 0 \text{ for at least one } i, k \quad (\text{A.3.12})$$

$$H_0 : (\tau\chi)_{il} = 0 \text{ for all } i, l \quad (\text{A.3.13})$$

$$H_1 : (\tau\chi)_{il} \neq 0 \text{ for at least one } i, l \quad (\text{A.3.14})$$

$$H_0 : (\beta\gamma)_{jk} = 0 \text{ for all } j, k \quad (\text{A.3.15})$$

$$H_1 : (\beta\gamma)_{jk} \neq 0 \text{ for at least one } j, k \quad (\text{A.3.16})$$

$$H_0 : (\beta\chi)_{jl} = 0 \text{ for all } j, l \quad (\text{A.3.17})$$

$$H_1 : (\beta\chi)_{jl} \neq 0 \text{ for at least one } j, l \quad (\text{A.3.18})$$

$$H_0 : (\gamma\chi)_{kl} = 0 \text{ for all } k, l \quad (\text{A.3.19})$$

$$H_1 : (\gamma\chi)_{kl} \neq 0 \text{ for at least one } k, l \quad (\text{A.3.20})$$

500 where H_0 and H_1 are the null and the alternative hypothesis respectively. The rejection of H_0 implies that at least one of the terms contributes significantly to the statistical model.

Now, to represent the totals of all observations under their correspondent levels we will use $y_{i...}$ for factor A , $y_{.j..}$ for factor B , $y_{..k.}$ for factor C , $y_{...l}$ for factor D , $y_{ij..}$ for all observations of the ij th cell, $y_{i.k.}$ for all observations of the ik th cell, $y_{i..l}$ for all observations of the il th cell, $y_{.jk.}$ for all observations of the jk th cell, $y_{.j.l}$ for all observations of the jl th cell, $y_{..kl}$ for all observations of the kl th cell and $y_{....}$ for the grand total of all observations. Then, $\bar{y}_{-i...}$, $\bar{y}_{-j..}$, $\bar{y}_{-...k.}$, $\bar{y}_{-...l}$, $\bar{y}_{-ij..}$, $\bar{y}_{-i.k.}$, $\bar{y}_{-i..l}$, $\bar{y}_{-.jk.}$, $\bar{y}_{-.j.l}$, $\bar{y}_{-..kl}$ and $\bar{y}_{-....}$, which denote the average of every previously described term, are computed as:

510

$$\begin{aligned}
y_{i\dots} &= \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{k=1}^c \sum_{l=1}^d y_{ijkl} & \bar{y}_{i\dots} &= \frac{y_{i\dots}}{bcd}, \\
y_{.j\dots} &= \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{k=1}^c \sum_{l=1}^d y_{ijkl} & \bar{y}_{.j\dots} &= \frac{y_{.j\dots}}{acd}, \\
y_{\dots k} &= \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{l=1}^d y_{ijkl} & \bar{y}_{\dots k} &= \frac{y_{\dots k}}{abd}, \\
y_{\dots l} &= \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{k=1}^c y_{ijkl} & \bar{y}_{\dots l} &= \frac{y_{\dots l}}{abc}, \\
y_{ij\dots} &= \sum_{k=1}^c \sum_{l=1}^d y_{ijkl} & \bar{y}_{ij\dots} &= \frac{y_{ij\dots}}{cd}, \\
y_{i\dots k} &= \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{l=1}^d y_{ijkl} & \bar{y}_{i\dots k} &= \frac{y_{i\dots k}}{bd}, \\
y_{i\dots l} &= \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{k=1}^c y_{ijkl} & \bar{y}_{i\dots l} &= \frac{y_{i\dots l}}{bc}, \\
y_{.jk\dots} &= \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{l=1}^d y_{ijkl} & \bar{y}_{.jk\dots} &= \frac{y_{.jk\dots}}{ad}, \\
y_{.j\dots l} &= \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{k=1}^c y_{ijkl} & \bar{y}_{.j\dots l} &= \frac{y_{.j\dots l}}{ac}, \\
y_{\dots kl} &= \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{j=1}^b y_{ijkl} & \bar{y}_{\dots kl} &= \frac{y_{\dots kl}}{ab}, \\
y_{\dots} &= \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{k=1}^c \sum_{l=1}^d y_{ijkl} & \bar{y}_{\dots} &= \frac{y_{\dots}}{abcd}
\end{aligned} \tag{A.4}$$

The total adjusted sum of squares of the model, $AdjSS_T$, is equal to the adjusted sum of squares of every single factor term, $AdjSS_A$, $AdjSS_B$, $AdjSS_C$ and $AdjSS_D$, the adjusted sum of squares of every interaction term, $AdjSS_{AB}$, $AdjSS_{AC}$, $AdjSS_{AD}$, $AdjSS_{BC}$, $AdjSS_{BD}$ and $AdjSS_{CD}$, and the adjusted sum of squares of

515 the error term, $AdjSS_E$. Each one of these terms is computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
AdjSS_T &= \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{k=1}^c \sum_{l=1}^d y_{ijkl}^2 - \bar{y}_{....}^2, \\
AdjSS_A &= \frac{1}{bcd} \sum_{i=1}^a y_{i...}^2 - \bar{y}_{....}^2, \\
AdjSS_B &= \frac{1}{acd} \sum_{j=1}^b y_{.j..}^2 - \bar{y}_{....}^2, \\
AdjSS_C &= \frac{1}{abd} \sum_{k=1}^c y_{...k.}^2 - \bar{y}_{....}^2, \\
AdjSS_D &= \frac{1}{abc} \sum_{l=1}^d y_{...l}^2 - \bar{y}_{....}^2, \\
AdjSS_{AB} &= \frac{1}{cd} \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{j=1}^b y_{ij..}^2 - \bar{y}_{....}^2 - AdjSS_A - AdjSS_B, \\
AdjSS_{AC} &= \frac{1}{bd} \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{k=1}^c y_{i.k.}^2 - \bar{y}_{....}^2 - AdjSS_A - AdjSS_C, \\
AdjSS_{AD} &= \frac{1}{bc} \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{l=1}^d y_{i..l}^2 - \bar{y}_{....}^2 - AdjSS_A - AdjSS_D, \\
AdjSS_{BC} &= \frac{1}{ad} \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{k=1}^c y_{.jk.}^2 - \bar{y}_{....}^2 - AdjSS_B - AdjSS_C, \\
AdjSS_{BD} &= \frac{1}{ac} \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{l=1}^d y_{.j.l}^2 - \bar{y}_{....}^2 - AdjSS_B - AdjSS_D, \\
AdjSS_{CD} &= \frac{1}{ab} \sum_{k=1}^c \sum_{l=1}^d y_{...kl}^2 - \bar{y}_{....}^2 - AdjSS_C - AdjSS_D, \\
AdjSS_E &= AdjSS_T - AdjSS_A - AdjSS_B - AdjSS_C - AdjSS_D \\
&\quad - AdjSS_{AB} - AdjSS_{AC} - AdjSS_{AD} - AdjSS_{BC} \\
&\quad - AdjSS_{BD} - AdjSS_{CD}
\end{aligned} \tag{A.5}$$

In an ANOVA context, the DoF are the amount of free data available to estimate the coefficient of every statistical term in the model. For instance, the total DoF is equal to the number of collapse multipliers obtained from the simulations minus one.

Every linear term in the model as a DoF equal to their number of levels minus one.

520 The addition of all DoF corresponding to the linear terms of the model provides the total DoF for the linear part of the model. The DoF of the interaction terms is equal to the product of the DoF from the corresponding linear terms. Similarly, the total DoF corresponding to the two-way interaction part of the model is equal to the addition of the DoF from the different two-way individual interaction terms. The DoF of the model

525 are equal to the sum of the DoF from its linear and two-way interaction parts. Finally, the DoF that correspond to the error term of the model are equal to the total DoF minus the DoF of the model. For further clarification, the DoF are computed as presented in Table A.1.

An adjusted mean of squares of a term is defined as the division of the adjusted

530 sum of squares value by its corresponding number of DoF. Thus, the adjusted average squares of a four factor design are computed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
AdjMS_A &= \frac{AdjSS_A}{DoF_A}, \\
AdjMS_B &= \frac{AdjSS_B}{DoF_B}, \\
AdjMS_C &= \frac{AdjSS_C}{DoF_C}, \\
AdjMS_D &= \frac{AdjSS_D}{DoF_D}, \\
AdjMS_{AB} &= \frac{AdjSS_{AB}}{DoF_{AB}}, \\
AdjMS_{AC} &= \frac{AdjSS_{AC}}{DoF_{AC}}, \\
AdjMS_{AD} &= \frac{AdjSS_{AD}}{DoF_{AD}}, \\
AdjMS_{BC} &= \frac{AdjSS_{BC}}{DoF_{BC}}, \\
AdjMS_{BD} &= \frac{AdjSS_{BD}}{DoF_{BD}}, \\
AdjMS_{CD} &= \frac{AdjSS_{CD}}{DoF_{CD}}, \\
AdjMS_E &= \frac{AdjSS_E}{DoF_E}
\end{aligned} \tag{A.6}$$

To test the statistical significance of everyone of the main and interaction terms of the statistical model, an F-test is performed. F-Values are computed by dividing the value of every adjusted mean of squares main and interaction term by the value of the adjusted mean of squares of the error term. Each one of these ratios will result into an F distribution with the corresponding DoF_x at the numerator and DoF_E at the denominator. Usually, the data will not support the null hypothesis tested if this ratio has large values. The critical region will be the upper tail of the F distribution. Finally, the P-Values are obtained using a F-test statistic table with the adequate DoF for the numerator and denominator of every statistical term tested.

The magnitude and importance of each one of the main factors and factor interaction effects were obtained and presented as Pareto charts of standardized effect. The Pareto chart of standardized effects is used to compare the relative magnitude and the statistical significance of the main parameters and of the two-way interaction terms in the response. Moreover, a reference line is also plotted in the Pareto chart in order to simplify the identification of the significant terms (every term with a standardized effect value higher than the reference line is considered to be statistically significant). This line is plotted at a value t , where t is the $1 - \alpha/2$ quantile of a t-distribution with DoF equal to DoF_E and α is the significance level of the test. Finally, standardized effects of every main and interaction term are computed as a Lenth's pseudo standard error (PSE) with the following method:

1. Compute the absolute value of the effects.
2. Calculate $S = 1.5$ median of effect in Step 1.
3. For the effects smaller than $2.5S$, compute the median.
4. $PSE = 1.5$ median calculated in Step 3.

The suitability of the adopted statistical models to describe the response, was measured as the values of the coefficient of determination, R^2 (equal to the regression sum of squares divided by the total sum of squares), and of the predicted coefficient of determination, R_{pred}^2 . Finally, the assumptions that the data was independent and normally distributed, in other words, that the analysed data was not affected by non-controlled parameters and that it roughly presents the shape of the Gauss curve, were visually validated by analysing the standardized residual plots of the response, α_c , its histogram and its normal probability plot.

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Table 2: ANOVA table of the pointed arches under load scenario A.

Source	DoF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Model	47	104.754	2.2288	979.62	0.000
Linear	10	96.165	9.6165	4226.73	0.000
Cohesion	2	83.457	41.7287	18340.95	0.000
Friction	3	0.182	0.0607	26.66	0.000
Sharpness	2	0.186	0.0929	40.85	0.000
Slenderness	3	12.340	4.1133	1807.91	0.000
Two-Way Interactions	37	8.588	0.2321	102.02	0.000
Cohesion-Friction	6	0.024	0.0040	1.76	0.115
Cohesion-Sharpness	4	0.115	0.0289	12.68	0.000
Cohesion-Slenderness	6	8.238	1.3729	603.45	0.000
Friction-Sharpness	6	0.133	0.0222	9.76	0.000
Friction-Slenderness	9	0.061	0.0068	2.98	0.004
Sharpness-Slenderness	6	0.017	0.0028	1.24	0.295
Error	96	0.218	0.0023		
Total	143	104.972			

DoF=Degrees of freedom, Adj SS= Adjusted sum of squares, Adj MS = Adjusted mean of squares.

Table 3: ANOVA table of the pointed arches under load scenario B.

Source	DoF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Model	56	7609438	135883	12.26	0.000
Linear	11	3825111	347737	31.38	0.000
Cohesion	2	1282242	641121	57.86	0.000
Friction	3	27056	9019	0.81	0.488
Slenderness	3	1297822	432607	39.04	0.000
Live load	3	1217991	405997	36.64	0.000
Two-Way Interactions	45	3784327	84096	7.59	0.000
Cohesion-Friction	6	5094	849	0.08	0.998
Cohesion-Slenderness	6	890816	148469	13.40	0.000
Cohesion-Live load	6	753611	125602	11.34	0.000
Friction-Slenderness	9	47035	5226	0.47	0.892
Friction-Live load	9	33687	3743	0.34	0.961
Slenderness-Live load	9	2054084	228232	20.60	0.000
Error	135	1495795	11080		
Total	191	9105233			

DoF=Degrees of freedom, Adj SS= Adjusted sum of squares, Adj MS = Adjusted mean of squares.

Table A.1: Computation of DoF for the ANOVA.

Source	DoF
Model	$DoF_{Model} = DoF_{Linear} + DoF_{Two-WayInteractions}$
Linear	$DoF_{Linear} = DoF_A + DoF_B + DoF_C + DoF_D$
A	$DoF_A = a - 1$
B	$DoF_B = b - 1$
C	$DoF_C = c - 1$
D	$DoF_D = d - 1$
Two-Way Interactions	$DoF_{Two-WayInteractions} = DoF_{AB} + DoF_{AC}$ $+ DoF_{AD} + DoF_{BC} + DoF_{BD} + DoF_{CD}$
A*B	$DoF_{AB} = DoF_A * DoF_B$
A*C	$DoF_{AC} = DoF_A * DoF_C$
A*D	$DoF_{AD} = DoF_A * DoF_D$
B*C	$DoF_{BC} = DoF_B * DoF_C$
B*D	$DoF_{BD} = DoF_B * DoF_D$
C*D	$DoF_{CD} = DoF_C * DoF_D$
Error	$DoF_{Error} = DoF_{Total} - DoF_{Model}$
Total	$DoF_{Total} = a * b * c * d - 1$